

Template - Processing analysis

Template to process all surfaces acquired with the LSM with the 50x/0.75 and 50x/0.95 objectives.

Processing

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_LSM_50x_type2_b_Topo		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:23:58 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	µm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	24.84	µm	
Size:	65532	digits	
Spacing:	0.3791	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII...filtered (As 2.500 μm)		
File path:	D:\Dropbox\jmmarreir...0x_type2_b_Topo.sur		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:23:58 PM		
Studiabile type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	0.000	μm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Offset:	-255.5	μm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.565	μm	
Min:	-2.556	μm	
Max:	2.009	μm	
Size:	120423	digits	
Spacing:	0.03791	nm	
NM-points ratio:	11.84 % (1065640 Pts)		

Identity card			
Name:	MudPlaster2015MEGII_...in non-measured points		
Created on:	4/12/2021 4:23:58 PM		
Studiable type:	Surface		
Axis:	X		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Y		
Length:	255.5	μm	
Size:	3000	points	
Spacing:	85.19	nm	
Axis:	Z		
Layer type:	Topography		
Length:	4.565	μm	
Size:	120423	digits	
Spacing:	0.03791	nm	
NM-points ratio:	0.000 % (0 Pts)		

Analyses

8. ISO 25178-2 parameters on surface #7

ISO 25178 - Primary surface			
<i>F: [Workflow] Form removed (LS-poly 3)</i>			
<i>S-filter (λs): [Workflow] S-filtered (λs 2.500 μm)</i>			
Height parameters			
Sq	0.7250	μm	
Ssk	-0.4928		
Sku	3.213		
Sp	2.002	μm	
Sv	2.563	μm	
Sz	4.565	μm	
Sa	0.5728	μm	
Functional parameters			
Smr	6.525	%	
Smc	0.8651	μm	
Sxp	1.702	μm	
Spatial parameters			
Sal	20.70	μm	
Str	*****		
Std	31.99	°	
Hybrid parameters			
Sdq	0.1767		
Sdr	1.446	%	
Functional parameters (Volume)			
Vm	0.02681	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vv	0.8919	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmp	0.02681	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vmc	0.6423	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvc	0.7866	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	
Vvv	0.1053	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	

Analyses:	
ISO 25178	8.
Furrow	9.
Texture direction	10.
Texture isotropy	11.
SSFA	12.

Warnings

Str: The autocorrelation lobe touches the edges. Try to level the...

9. Furrow analysis on surface #7

All furrows are shown.

Parameters	Value	Unit
Maximum depth of furrows	2.938	µm
Mean depth of furrows	0.7010	µm
Mean density of furrows	3529	cm/cm2

10. Texture direction on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
First direction	89.98	°
Second direction	135.0	°
Third direction	45.01	°

11. Texture isotropy on surface #7

Parameters	Value	Unit
Texture isotropy	51.89	%

12. SSFA on surface #7

